

Studies in Alcoholysis. Part I.

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Replacement of one alcoholic group by another in esters has been studied in detail.* Haller (*Compt. rend.*, 1906, 143, 657), whose experiments confirmed the views of Lewkowitsch (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1903, 22, 592), converted glycerides into methyl esters of the constituent fatty acids by treating them with methyl alcohol in the presence of hydrochloric acid. The alcoholysis occurred in stages as was found by Grun (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1919, I, 222).

It has been found by Haller and other workers that alcoholysis proceeds easily up to the glycerides of C₁₂- acid after which it becomes irregular and upon this observation Fendler (*Mitt. a. d. Pharm. Institut der Univ. Berlin*) apparently has tried to base his "distillation value" calculated from the results of "ethanolysis" by which he proposes to determine the percentages of cocoanut oil (which has a higher Polenske value and as such should yield greater quantity of ethyl laurate in the process of alcoholysis) in butter fat.

The problem of detection of cocoanut oil in butter fat is in reality a very intricate one and it has been found in practice that adulteration with a small percentage of cocoanut oil, especially if backed by lard or tallow, hardly affects the wide ranges of the different values of butter fat. It was thought that if some suitable catalyst other than hydrochloric acid could be found, which would effect selective "alcoholysis" on C₁₂-glycerides then such sort of detection of adulteration, although lengthy, would be a sure one.

With this idea the present work was begun and the following new catalysts were tried:—Benzenestearosulphonic acid, naphthalene-

* Kolhatkar, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 921 ; Sudborough and Bhagwat, *J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1918, 2, 121 ; Sudborough and Karvel, *J. Indian. Inst. Sci.*, 1919, 3, 1 ; Darsanacharyya and Sudborough, *J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1921, 4, 181 ; Goldschmidt, Gorbitz, Hougen and Pable, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1921, 99, 116.

stearosulphonic acid (Twitchell's reagents), pyridine, piperidine, piperidine hydrochloride and phosphorus oxychloride. The results so far obtained have not fulfilled the expectation of selective alcoholysis but it has been found that phosphorus oxychloride can form a convenient substitute for hydrochloric acid. The results are comparable. In the Haller's hydrochloric acid method, the acid gas is required to be pure and dry and there are additional manipulative difficulties with regard to exact increase in weight and moreover when the ether-alcoholic solution is heated on the water-bath the amount of the catalysts must inevitably suffer loss in weight, as much of the acid escapes. But in the case of phosphorus oxychloride the required amount may be added at once and proper check may be made strictly with accurate weight of the catalyst. As this method may simplify in future the alcoholysis of numerous unexamined oils, the results obtained are published.

It was observed that under proper precautions benzenestearosulphonic acid and naphthalenestearosulphonic acid do not cause any appreciable alcoholysis, if traces of mineral acids are carefully excluded. Alcoholysis observed by Hallen with phenolsulphonic acid is probably due to the presence of traces of mineral acid. Clarification of this issue, as also the action of other catalysts will be the subject of a future communication.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Benzenestearosulphonic Acid.—To a mixture of 30 c.c. of benzene and 30 c.c. of oleic acid, a large excess of concentrated sulphuric acid was added slowly avoiding rise in temperature. After several hours the reaction mixture was boiled with water, the lower layer was removed, the upper layer being washed by water containing hydrochloric acid till it was free from sulphuric acid. The mixture was then dissolved in ether and shaken with water. The aqueous extract was then treated with a little hydrochloric acid (the reagent is insoluble in water acidulated with hydrochloric acid), taken up with ether, again extracted with water and the water evaporated off; the hydrochloric acid is then completely removed by heating in an air-oven at 100° for several hours (Twitchell, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1900, 22, 22).

Preparation of Naphthalenestearosulphonic Acid.—Oleic acid (100 parts) was placed in a dry vassel with naphthalene (30 parts),

the mixture being warmed till solution took place. It was then cooled to 50° by stirring in order to prevent the naphthalene settling out as a solid mass at the bottom. Sulphuric acid (66° B_é, 300 parts) having 99.2 p. c. sulphuric acid, was run in at first drop by drop to avoid violent reaction taking place and the mixture was well stirred. The temperature kept below 50°. When all the acid had been added the mixture was poured into twice the volume of cold water, well-stirred and allowed to settle overnight. The reagent appeared as a thick layer at the top of the water, which was then separated and dried in air-oven (Twitchell, *loc. cit.*, p. 25).

Alcoholysis. — In each case 50 c.c. of cocoanut oil well dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate were taken; this was mixed with 125 c.c. of anhydrous ether (kept for a fortnight over sodium wire and distilled) and 75 c.c. of anhydrous methyl alcohol (dried over quick lime and distilled) and boiled under reflux gently with the catalyst on the water-bath for 4 hours. In the case of hydrochloric acid gas it was first of all dried by concentrated sulphuric acid and passed through methyl alcohol until the requisite weight was gained. The other catalysts were first accurately weighed and then added to methyl alcohol a little at a time.

After the reaction (after 4 hours) the ether alcoholic solution of the esters was neutralised (excepting in the cases of pyridine, piperidine and piperidine hydrochloride) with barium carbonate with constant shaking. The ether and methyl alcohol were then distilled off and the residue in the flask was taken up with ether. The ethereal solution was repeatedly washed with brine to remove glycerol, excess of barium carbonate, etc., and then dried over freshly ignited anhydrous magnesium sulphate overnight. The magnesium sulphate was filtered off through a Gooch and washed with dry ether; the collected ethereal solution was then distilled on the water-bath to drive away ether and the residual liquid was then fractionated at 16-17 mm. pressure. The fractions were collected at ranges comprising approximately the midpoints between the boiling points of the esters at 15-17 mm. pressure which are as follows:—

	B. p. at 15-17 mm.		B. p. at 15-17 mm.
Methyl caproate	52.5°	Methyl laurate	141°
„ caprylate	83°	„ myristate	167.5°
„ caprate	114°	„ palmitate	176°

TABLE I.

Catalysts used.	Amount of catalyst taken.	Methyl esters collected at 15-17 mm.			
		Up to 100°.	100°-30°.	130°-55°.	155°-83°.
Benzenestearosulphonic acid containing traces of hydrochloric acid.	1.72 g.	1.5 c.c.	2.5 c.c.	7.8 c.c.	—
Benzenestearosulphonic acid free from hydrochloric acid.	2.95	0	0	2	—
Pyridine	1.72	—	—	—	Practically nil.
Piperidine	1.7	0.5	1	3	—
Piperidine hydrochloride	1.72	0	0	0	Practically nil.
Hydrochloric acid gas	2.95	3	9	26.2	9.2 c.c.
Phosphorus oxychloride	2.95	4.2	7.2	26.5	9.2

TABLE II.

Catalysts used.	Amount of catalyst taken.	Methyl esters collected at 16-17 mm.			
		Up to 100°.	100-30°.	130-55°.	155-83°.
I. Naphthalenestearosulphonic acid containing traces of sulphuric acid.	3.57 g.	2 c.c.	6 c.c.	10 c.c.	8.5 c.c.
II* "	1.72	0	0	0.75	1.2

* Contained different amount of sulphuric acid.

TABLE III.

Catalysts used.	Amount of catalyst taken.	Methyl esters collected at 15-17 mm.			
		Up to 100°.	100-30°.	130-55°.	155-83°.
Hydrochloric acid gas	3.56 g.	3 c.c.	11 c.c.	26 c.c.	9.5 c.c.
Phosphorus oxychloride	3.56	3	10.5	24.5	8.5